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Graduates in the Italian regions

Between 2005 and 2019 they increased by 28.77%

The Istat-Bes calculates the value of the percentage of people who have completed at least the upper secondary school on the total of people who have between 25 and 64 years of age.

Ranking of the Italian regions by number of people with at least the diploma. Umbria is in the first place for people's value with at least the diploma with a value of 71.3, followed by Lazio with a value of 70.3 units and by Friuli-Venezia Giulia with an amount of 70.1 unit. In the middle of the standings there are the brands with a value of 65.3, Tuscany with a value of 64.8 units and Veneto with a value of 64.7 units. Campania close the ranking with a value equal to 52.9 units, followed by Sicily with a value of 51.8 units and from Puglia with a value of 51.3 units.

Ranking of the Italian regions by number of people with at least the diploma between 2005 and 2019. Sardinia is in the first place due to percentage variation of people with at least the diploma between 2005 and 2020 with a value of 37.91% or equal to an amount of 14.9 units, followed by Veneto with a value of 37.08% equal to an amount of 17.5 units, and by the Aosta Valley with a value of 36.04% equal to a amount of 16.4 units. In the middle of the standings there are Piedmont with an amount of 30.93% and a value of 15 units, followed by Puglia with a value of 28.25% equal to an amount of 11.3, and by Molise with a value of 26.98% equal to an amount of 13.3 units. Liguria close the ranking with a value of 21.52% equal to an amount of 12.2 units, Lazio with a value of 18.55% equal to an amount of 11 units and Calabria with a variation equal to An amount of 17.38% equal to an amount of 8.1 units. Overall, the average value of people with the diploma grew up an amount of 28.77% equal to an amount of 14 units.

Italian macro-regions. The number of graduates in Northern Italy grew in the period between 2004 and 2019 from an amount of 50.50 units up to a value of 65.70 units or a variation equal to an amount of 15.20 units equal to an amount of 30.10%. In Central Italy the value of the number of graduates grew from an amount of 54.90 units up to a value of 68.10 units or equal to a variation of 13.20 units equal to an amount of 24.04%. The number of graduates in the South has grown from an amount of 42.70 units up to a value of 54.00 units or equal to a variation of 11.30 units equal to a value of 26.46%. Overall, the value of graduates in Italian macro-regions between 2004 and 2019 grew from an amount of 48.70 units up to a value of 62.20 units or equal to a variation of 13.50 units equal to 27.72 %.

Clusterization with K-means algorithm optimized with the silhouette coefficient. Below is a modeling model using the K-means algorithm optimized with the silhouette coefficient. The analysis highlights the existence of two different Clusters or:

- Cluster 1: Emilia-Romagna, Friuli-Venezia Giulia, Marche, Abruzzo, Lombardy, Trentino-Alto Adige, Liguria, Umbria, Lazio, Veneto, Piedmont, Tuscany, Molise, Basilicata;
- Cluster 2: Sicily, Sardinia, Campania, Puglia, Calabria, Valle d'Aosta.

From the point of view of the Clusters median it is possible to observe that the median value of the 1-C1 cluster is equal to an amount of 66.5 units while the median value of the 2-C2 cluster is equal to 53.55 units. The following system of the Clusters or $C1 = 66.5 > C2 = 53.55$ derives. From a

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geographical point of view there is therefore a distinction between Central-North Italy with high values of the number of graduates and southern Italy with reduced values. However, not all regions of southern Italy are part of the second Clusters, there are also some who are included in the first cluster such as Molise, Basilicata, and Abruzzo. In addition, the 2-C2 cluster is not only including the southern regions and in fact also includes the Aosta Valley. However, it is possible to find a substantial contrast between Central-North and Southern Italy which offers further specification, this time of school type, to the traditional economic-financial determination of the Italian gap.

Network Analysis with the use of Manhattan's distance. The method of distance of Manhattan is used below to verify the presence of network structures in the structure of data relating to the presence of graduates in the Italian regions. The analysis shows the presence of a complex network structure and 4 simplified structures. The complex structure is complex consists of Sicily, Puglia, and Sardinia. In particular, the following relationships exist or:

- Sicily has a connection with Puglia equal to a value of 0.6, and a link with Sardinia equal to a value of 0.44 units;
- Sardinia has a relationship with Puglia for a value of 0.47 and with Sicily for a value of 0.44;
- Puglia has a relationship with Sicily for a value of 0.6 and with Sardinia with a value of 0.47.
- In addition, the following simplified structures are present or:
- Basilicata and Molise are connected with a link value equal to an amount of 0.5 units;
- Emilia-Romagna and Friuli-Venezia Giulia are connected with a link value of 0.42 units;
- Veneto and Piedmont are connected with a link with a value of 0.55 units;
- Marche and Lombardy are connected with a link having a value of 0.25 units.

The structure with complex network if compared to couponing seems to confirm the presence of a relationship between some southern regions or Sardinia, Puglia and Sicily, while on the other hand the relationships between the regions of Cluster 1 are frayed and lack to present elements of complexity.

Machine Learning and Predictions. Below is a model of Machine Learning for the prediction of the future value of graduates in the Italian regions. 10 algorithms analyzed on the basis of the ability to minimize statistical errors MSE, RMSE, Mae and to maximize R2 are considered. The algorithms were trained using 80% of data through the use of cross validation. Based on this classification, the following ranking of the algorithms is then presented or:

- SGD with a payoff value of 4;
- KNN with a payoff value of 10;
- Random Forest with a payoff value of 11;
- Gradient Boosting with a payoff value of 15;
- Linear Regression with a payoff value of equal to 21;
- Adaboost with a payoff value of 23;
- Tree with a payoff value of 28;
- SVM with a payoff value of 32;
- Costant with a payoff value of 36;
- Neural Network with a payoff value of 40.

Through the use of the most performing algorithm or SGD it is therefore possible to verify the regions that are Winners and Losers in terms of growth or reduction of the number of graduates. The SGD algorithm predicts the following regions Winners-ons regions that have a value of the number of graduates who has been growing up growing:

- Calabria with a growth of 54.7 units up to a value of 56.92 units or equal to a value of 2.22 units equal to a value of 4.06%;
- Campania with a variation of 52.9 units up to a value of 54.57 units or equal to a value of 1.67 units equal to a value of 3.16%;
- Lazio with a variation from an amount of 70.3 units up to a value of 72.37 units or a growth of 2.07 units equal to an amount of 2.94%;

Furthermore, the most significant diminutive variations are indicated below, namely those Losers regions, i.e. regions for which the SGD algorithm predicts a significant diminutive variation. These regions are:

- Valle d'Aosta with a variation from an amount of 61.9 units up to a value of 60.21 units or equal to a variation of -1.69 units equal to a variation of -2.73%;
- Friuli Venezia Giulia with a variation from an amount of 70.14 up to a value of 68.11 units or equal to a variation of -2.03 units equal to a value of -2.89%;
- Sardinia with a diminutive variation from an amount of 54.2 units up to a value of 51.84 units or equal to a variation of -2.36 units or equal to a variation of -4.35%.

However, it is also possible to use algorithms to calculate the probability of a region to overcome the average Italian value by number of graduates. In this case, a new variable is built consisting of the difference between the average value of the number of graduates in Italy and the number of graduates by region. In the event that the variation is positive, a value equal to 1 is assigned otherwise a value of 0 is assigned. In this sense, algorithms are analyzed in terms of accuracy. The analysis shows the presence of the following orders in terms of accuracy or:

- Gradient Boosting, Adaboost, Naive Bayes have an accuracy value of 1;
- kNN, Tree, Random Forest, SVM, Neural Network, CN2 Rule, Logistic Regression and SGD have an accuracy value of 0.95;
- Costant has an accuracy value of 0.7.

Conclusions. The analysis shows that the number of graduates in the Italian regions has significantly increased between 2005 and 2019. However, there are significant distinctions between Central-North Italy and Southern Italy in terms of number of graduates. If on the one hand in the regions of Northern Italy in the population between 25 and 64 years there are about 66 graduates out of 100 people this value is 54.00 out of 100 in the regions of the South. That is, for every 100 people in the age group 25-64 years in northern Italy there are 12 graduates more than in the South. Obviously, these data are quantitative and do not have the ability to highlight what are the qualitative differences, which also exist, teaching models between north and southern Italy. Furthermore, it must be considered that these values do not even consider the types of educational institutions attended by students. The graduates in the South are therefore less than those of Northern Italy and most likely also have a type of training qualitatively reduced with tendency to school structures less adequate. In addition, it should be considered that obviously a smaller number of graduates tends to reflect also in terms of reducing the number of students enrolled in university institutions. Finally, it is necessary to detect that the data analyzed refer to 2019 and that these values probably have significantly worsened during the Covid 19 pandemic. In fact, the lockdown, and the forms of teaching at a distance have substantially worsened the quality of the school training and have promoted the phenomenon of school abandonment. Finally, it is very likely that the low number of graduates in southern Italy compared to other areas of Italy reflects a more serious condition than the southern population or the fact of no longer seeing in school and training an essential element for economic, social growth, civil,

individual and collective. A skepticism towards culture that risks burdening even more on the delay in the South especially in the current international economic context characterized by the domain of the economy of knowledge and technological innovation. In this regard, it is therefore necessary that Italian and European economic policies give more resources to the economies of the South to make sure that the number of graduates of Southern Italy reaches at least the average Italian level.

Declarations

Acknowledgment. I want to thank the colleagues of the Lum Enterprise S.r.l. and prof. Alberto Costantiello and Lucio Laureti of LUM University Giuseppe Degennaro.

Data Availability Statement. The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

Funding. The author received no financial support for the research, authorship, and/or publication of this article.

Declaration of Competing Interest. The author declares that there is no conflict of interests regarding the publication of this manuscript. In addition, the ethical issues, including plagiarism, informed consent, misconduct, data fabrication and/or falsification, double publication and/or submission, and redundancies have been completely observed by the authors.

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Appendix

	2004	2005	2006	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019
Piemonte	48,5	50,8	52,7	53,6	54,2	55,1	56,9	57,6	57,8	59,3	60,6	61,4	60,9	61,3	62,9	63,5
Valle d'Aosta/Vallée d'Aoste	45,5	46,6	46,3	47,8	48,1	49,4	50,4	51,8	54	55,1	56	56,7	58,2	59,7	61,1	61,9
Liguria	56,7	58,3	58,3	59,1	62,8	64,2	63,2	63,5	63,5	63,2	63,9	64	63,8	65	67,2	68,9
Lombardia	51,3	53,1	54,1	55,4	56,5	56,9	57,8	58,6	59,9	61,2	62,1	63,1	63,2	64,1	65	64,5
Trentino-Alto Adige/Südtirol	51,1	52,7	53,8	57,3	58,8	59,8	60,5	61,3	62,8	64,9	68,5	68,1	68,2	69,5	69,7	69,3
Veneto	47,2	49,5	50,5	53	54,6	55,7	57,6	57,4	58,4	59,7	61,3	61,5	62,4	63,9	64,6	64,7
Friuli-Venezia Giulia	51,6	53,1	56,2	56,8	57,8	58	59,3	58,2	62,5	63,4	64,6	65,5	66,5	67,6	68,6	70,1
Emilia-Romagna	52,3	53,7	55,3	56,7	57,9	59,2	60,1	61,1	62,2	63,4	64,6	65,4	66,4	67	68,1	69
Toscana	48,9	49,9	51,9	50,7	52,6	54,4	54,9	55,4	56,5	57,9	60	62,4	63,7	64,8	64,9	64,8
Umbria	57	58,4	59,6	60	61,1	62,5	64,2	66,1	67,1	66	67,1	68	67,9	68	68,4	71,3
Marche	52,3	53,6	54,6	55,2	55,8	57,3	57,6	58,1	60	61,4	62,9	64,1	63,6	64,5	64,9	65,3
Lazio	59,3	61	61,2	63	64,2	65,1	65,2	66,3	67,6	68,3	70,1	69,6	69,1	69,7	69,9	70,3
Abruzzo	53,7	56	57,2	54,9	56,7	56,8	58,8	61,8	64,4	65,1	63,2	63,4	63,5	64,8	66,6	67,7
Molise	49,3	50,5	51,4	52,9	53,1	53,6	53,2	52,6	56	57,5	58,4	59,4	59	60	62,2	62,6
Campania	42,6	43	43,6	43,5	43,6	45,3	46,1	47,4	49,7	50,8	51,2	51,3	52	52,8	53	52,9
Puglia	40	40,2	42,3	43,7	43,9	43	44,5	46,4	46,3	47,3	48,8	48,4	48,9	49,3	50,2	51,3
Basilicata	47,1	49,2	50,3	50,8	52,8	53,7	53,1	54,1	55,6	57	58	59,2	60	60,5	61,5	62,6
Calabria	46,6	47,6	48,2	48,5	49,1	50,9	50,7	51,8	53,2	53,1	53,6	54,5	53,3	54,4	54,1	54,7
Sicilia	41,1	42	43	43,6	44,2	45,9	46,5	47,1	48,3	48,1	49,2	49,8	49,7	49,9	51,4	51,8
Sardegna	39,3	40,3	42,1	43,5	44,4	44,6	46	47,6	47,8	47,8	47,2	49,6	49,7	50,5	51,5	54,2

Persone con almeno il diploma (25-64 anni)

Variazione del valore dei diplomati tra il 2005 ed il 2019.

Rank	Regioni	Var Assoluta	Var Percentuale
1	Sardegna	★ 14,9	★ 37,91
2	Veneto	★ 17,5	★ 37,08
3	Valle d'Aosta	★ 16,4	★ 36,04
4	Friuli-Venezia Giulia	★ 18,5	★ 35,85
5	Trentino-Alto Adige	★ 18,2	★ 35,62
6	Basilicata	★ 15,5	★ 32,91
7	Toscana	★ 15,9	★ 32,52
8	Emilia-Romagna	★ 16,7	★ 31,93
9	Piemonte	★ 15	★ 30,93
10	Puglia	★ 11,3	★ 28,25
11	Molise	★ 13,3	★ 26,98
12	Abruzzo	★ 14	★ 26,07
13	Sicilia	★ 10,7	★ 26,03
14	Lombardia	★ 13,2	★ 25,73
15	Umbria	★ 14,3	★ 25,09
16	Marche	★ 13	★ 24,86
17	Campania	★ 10,3	★ 24,18
18	Liguria	★ 12,2	★ 21,52
19	Lazio	★ 11	★ 18,55
20	Calabria	★ 8,1	★ 17,38

Variazione del valore dei diplomati tra il 2005 ed il 2019.

Variazione del valore dei diplomati tra il 2005 ed il 2019.

Model	MSE	RMSE	MAE	R2
SGD	1.984	1.409	1.201	0.952
kNN	3.480	1.866	1.473	0.916
Random Forest	3.500	1.871	1.399	0.916
Gradient Boosting	4.469	2.114	1.439	0.892
Linear Regression	5.275	2.297	1.961	0.873
AdaBoost	6.226	2.495	1.505	0.850
Tree	9.815	3.133	2.222	0.764
SVM	21.204	4.605	3.496	0.490
Constant	46.050	6.786	5.533	-0.108
Neural Network	1402.730	37.453	32.608	-32.752

2019	Regioni	kNN	Tree	Random Forest	Gradient Boosting	SVM	Neural Network	Linear Regression	AdaBoost	Constant	SGD
54.2	Sardegna	54.52	52.675	53.5758	51.7781	61.13	64.0486	52.4726	51.8	63.5368	51.9877
52.9	Campania	54.78	53	54.3154	53.419	60.7601	52.5065	51.0473	54.2	63.6053	54.9236
51.8	Sicilia	55	53.275	52.9272	53.2478	60.8937	60.1676	53.9595	52.9	63.6632	52.7039
51.3	Puglia	55.1	53.4	53.2767	51.9983	61.3213	69.309	49.1073	51.8	63.6895	51.9464
54.7	Calabria	58.36	62.65	59.1768	60.5448	61.1578	29.7356	58.4592	61.9	63.5105	56.7467
61.9	Valle d'Aosta/V...	61.64	54.45	57.6652	56.1617	61.0023	23.973	60.2351	54.7	63.1316	59.7627
62.6	Molise	63.5	62.6667	63.4483	62.431	63.1431	7.93994	62.447	62.6	63.0947	61.8947
62.6	Basilicata	63.5	62.6667	63.3468	62.8338	62.9053	10.5093	57.7105	62.6	63.0947	62.0154
64.8	Toscana	63.58	62.65	64.2202	63.2015	63.9135	5.83695	66.6222	64.7	62.9789	64.7377
63.5	Piemonte	63.84	64.825	64.2291	64.2707	64.4011	6.97743	62.0085	64.5	63.0474	63.782
64.7	Veneto	64.14	64.8667	64.2065	63.6596	64.2691	8.01828	64.169	64.5	62.9842	65.1395
64.5	Lombardia	66.52	68.5333	64.4185	65.9413	66.2873	19.355	66.0464	65.3	62.9947	65.8486
65.3	Marche	66.96	68.5333	65.1231	65.5791	66.5041	20.9779	64.4371	64.7	62.9526	65.8754
70.1	Friuli-Venezia G...	67.16	68.725	66.937	68.6017	66.3563	31.2436	69.3316	68.9	62.7	68.16
69.0	Emilia-Romagna	67.38	70.25	69.8333	70.2134	66.5787	33.0332	72.0173	70.1	62.7579	68.3827
67.7	Abruzzo	67.56	64.825	65.4443	67.3617	66.1243	30.5355	71.0125	68.9	62.8263	66.8359
69.3	Trentino-Alto A...	68.68	64.825	68.3653	70.1856	66.4761	39.4858	71.4983	70.1	62.7421	70.8556
71.3	Umbria	69.04	69.9	69.1216	70.1491	66.5448	55.6525	69.6299	69.3	62.6368	70.5708
68.9	Liguria	69.48	70.25	69.3701	69.4995	66.3553	44.6396	65.5118	69.3	62.7632	66.993
70.3	Lazio	69.72	70.2333	69.6672	71.1939	65.5666	72.8602	70.5179	71.3	62.6895	72.741

	Algoritmo	MSE	RMSE	MAE	R2
1	SGD	0	0.00000	0.00000	1.00000
2	kNN	0.00122915	0.0149473	0.0106451	0.9987541
3	Random Forest	0.00157248	0.0183796	0.0055926	0.9984278
4	Gradient Boosti...	0.00193509	0.0218119	0.0095647	0.9980421
5	Linear Regression	0.0025104	0.0268774	0.0261519	0.9974785
6	AdaBoost	0.00318921	0.0323581	0.0116619	0.9967962
7	Tree	0.00575101	0.0500180	0.0344455	0.9942450
8	SVM	0.0138804	0.0907631	0.0749285	0.9861169
9	Costant	0.0316152	0.1511335	0.1396568	0.9683773
10	Neural Network	1	1.00000	1.00000	0.00000

Model	AUC	$\hat{CA}$	F1	Precision	Recall
Constant	0.000	0.700	0.576	0.490	0.700
kNN	0.988	0.950	0.949	0.953	0.950
Tree	0.917	0.950	0.949	0.953	0.950
SVM	0.988	0.950	0.949	0.953	0.950
Neural Network	0.988	0.950	0.949	0.953	0.950
CN2 rule inducer	0.988	0.950	0.949	0.953	0.950
Logistic Regression	1.000	0.950	0.949	0.953	0.950
SGD	0.917	0.950	0.949	0.953	0.950
Random Forest	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000
Gradient Boosting	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000
AdaBoost	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000
Naive Bayes	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000

